

SYNODALITY AS A FRUIT OF THE VATICAN COUNCIL II

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7178863

Fabio Antunes do Nascimento

Doctoral candidate in Theology at CEBITEPAL – CELAM, Bogotá in Colombia, Master in Pastoral Theology at CEBITEPAL – CELAM, priest and Diocesan Pastoral Coordinator of the Diocese of Coxim - MS, Professor of Pastoral Theology at UCDB, fabiopjms@hotmail.com

Cesar Augusto Ramirez Giraldo

Doctor of Theology and Dr. in Philosophy - Full Professor Universidad Pontificia Bolivariana de Medellín - Colombia. cesar.ramirez@upb.edu.com

Summary

This article seeks to contribute to the reflection on synodality in the life of the Church in the light of Pope Francis' Magisterium. From the ecclesiology of the Second Vatican Council emerged the awareness of the need for ecclesial renewal from its foundations. In a process of continuity, we can place synodality as one more stage of this ecclesial development, a constitutive category of the Church's identity, since its origin, in the Trinitarian communion. As well as current in its pastoral challenge of making the immutable truth of the Gospel applicable in the present time. In this perspective, we propose how this search, by the Pilgrim Church, can advance with ecclesial renewal from synodality in parishes, with processes as suggested by the International Theological Commission in its document on synodality, when they propose a process of implementation of: events, style and synodal structures. In this sense, we reflect on the governance structures in the parish - Parish Priest, Pastoral Council and Economic Council - suggesting that small changes in their character can trigger this pastoral conversion from the perspective of synodality. The subject of this article is the result of research in the process of Doctorate in Theology by CEBITEPAL (Centro Bíblico Teológico Pastoral para América Latina y el Caribe) and CELAM (Council Episcopal Latin American and Caribbean) at UPB (Universidad Pontificia Bolivariana) of Medellín, Colombia .

Keywords: Synodality. parishes. Pastoral Conversion

1. Introduction

The Synod of Bishops is a concrete fruit of the Second Vatican Council created by Pope Paul VI in 1965 by the *Motu Proprio APOSTOLICA SOLLICITUDO: ISTITUZIONE DEL SINODO DEI VESCOVI PER LA CHIESA UNIVERSALE* (Institution of the Synod of Bishops for the Universal Church), collaborated in the development and application of conciliar

documents. Since the beginning of his ministry, Pope Francis has provoked the Synods to delve into important themes in the life of the Church, such as: family, young people, the Amazon, etc. In this way, he has valued this body and integrated other participants that are not just the ordinary delegate bishops. Now, Pope Francis proposes a Synod on synodality as a constitutive category in his pontificate: sometimes through gestures such as the permanent group of cardinals who help in the government of the Church; sometimes through events such as the synods themselves and the publication of the International Theological Commission (CTI) on synodality.

From the initial expectation that Francis would carry out a reform of the Church, from a profound change announced by the Roman Curia, but not yet announced, to a certain frustration of the most daring, after the post-synodal exhortations, what is certain is that, in little more than eight years ago, Francis promoted several acts that renew and trigger the expected renewal in the Church. In the wake of this movement, the Church is moving towards the realization of a Synod that can give a broader meaning to the theological-pastoral category of synodality.

Thus, we can say that the pontificate of Francis has promoted what the CTI calls the graduality of synodality – style, events and organisms –, which converges to the realization of a Synod on synodality. In fact, synodality advanced vigorously in two areas, namely: in theological reflection and in the Magisterium of Pope Francis. Also added to these areas are the events in which the synodal style is promoted, such as the last two synods, namely: the one held on the Amazon and the Ecclesial Assembly, scheduled for November 2021.

A great challenge in the process of implementing synodality in the life of the Church is to reconcile this ecclesial identity with the structure of the parish. In the ecclesial imagination, the parish “is the figure of the Church and its most public image. For the majority of the baptized, it is the place and the scope in which the ecclesial becomes accessible and experienced” (ISP, 2018). Our fundamental question is to find that “great plasticity”, which the Pope indicates for the parish, when he says that it “is not an outdated structure [...], if it is able to constantly reform and adapt” (EG 28, 2013).

Our objective is to collaborate in the search for this plasticity, as well as to indicate paths that can start, without drastically thinking about the extinction of the parish, nor pretentiously proposing a punctual act that in itself will completely transform the parish. We think of processes that, once initiated, are progressively articulating and taking shape, as suggested by the CTI: creating events, organism and synodal style.

For that, we think that it is possible to trigger the process of “synodalization” with the recognition of the Ecclesial Missionary Communities and the effectiveness of the Pastoral and Economic Councils for governance in the parish. Furthermore, overcoming the centralism of the parish, configuring it as a community of communities and, at the same time, promoting the protagonism of lay people overcoming clericalism, which are enormous challenges that require a process of pastoral conversion.

From the description of how the term synodality has been used after the Second Vatican Ecumenical Council, mainly from its official documents, we can recognize the evolution that this category has undergone over the years. Because even if it is not explicitly about synodality, the Magisterium of the Popes, the Episcopal Conferences and the reflection of theologians have created conditions for the growth of this sphere. So, together on this path, we want to collaborate in a qualitative way in the development of synodality in the life of the Church, with the revision of texts that contribute to this paradigmatic ecclesial moment of the synod on synodality, in particular, of how to implement this style in the structure of the parish .

2 The evolution of the synodality category

On the occasion of the fiftieth anniversary of the institution of the Synod of Bishops, by Pope Saint Paul VI, Pope Francis defined synodality as follows: synodality, as a constitutive dimension of the Church, offers us the most appropriate interpretative framework for understanding the hierarchical ministry itself. If we understand that, as Saint John Chrysostom says, “Church and Synod are synonymous”, – for the Church is nothing more than this 'walking together' of the Flock of God along the paths of history to meet Christ the Lord –, we will also understand that within it no one can be “raised” above others.

In Francis' words, synodality is characteristic of the Church's identity, much more than a governance structure, but an ecclesial expression of communion. In a concrete way, synodality was expressed in an important “organ of pastoral governance of the Church” (Paul VI, 1965) born of the Second Vatican Ecumenical Council, the Synod of Bishops. Also at other levels of the Church, diocesan and national synods were developed, as well as the Assemblies and Conferences of Bishops, which act in a synodal style. In addition, notably, the impulse of Francis in his pontificate has provoked the deepening of synodality, especially by the convening of a Synod on this topic, in which the whole Church is invited to participate: “ *Per una Chiesa sinodale: comunione, partecipazione e missione* ”³²(Synod of Bishops, 2021).

³²trans. by the author: “For a Synodal Church: community, participatory and missionary”.

In 2018 the International Theological Commission published a study entitled: Synodality in the life and mission of the Church. This study is an impetus for the deepening of this category that was reborn with the Second Vatican Council, but which according to the CTI “there are many steps that still need to be taken in the direction outlined by the Council (CTI 8, 2018). Thus, synodality does not appear as a replacement for the images of the Church as the Sacrament and People of God in “*Lumen Gentium*”, but a tool to make them concrete.

In addition to the documents of the Magisterium and the reflections of theologians on synodality, various ecclesial events and organizations collaborated in the development of the concept of synodality. From the beginning of his pontificate, Francis constituted a council of cardinals to assist in the project of reforming the Roman Curia. The Synods of Bishops, celebrated during this period, were also expanded by the participation of experts, guests, especially women, so that the Synod of the Amazon, for example, stood out for this broad participation of delegates, and not only of bishops.

Synodality emerges as a theological-pastoral category in development, with this process being tracked in two directions. In the first of biblical foundation and ecclesial Tradition, to demonstrate that in the sources of Christianity the synodal style was constitutive. In the second, the development of synodality, as suggested by the CTI, implementing synod style, events and bodies, as indicated by Pope Francis: “The path of synodality is precisely the path that God expects from the Church of the third millennium” (Francis, 2017).

Francis' initiatives in various areas sow synodality in the Church's vast field. Examples of this can be cited: *Scholas Occurrentes*³³, Economy of Francisco³⁴, *Piattaforma Laudato Si*³⁵ and the Global Educational Pact. In addition to the ecclesiastical scope, Pope Francis has created paths of dialogue and systematically promoting fraternity, as presented in his latest Encyclical *Fratelli Tutti*, 2020.

³³ **Scholas Occurrentes** : It is an organization of pontifical right, which was born in Buenos Aires on the initiative of the then Archbishop Jorge Bergoglio, now Pope Francis. It is an international network that unites students from all over the world around an educational program based on art, sport and technology. The objective is to promote social integration and the culture of encounter and inclusion in schools.

³⁴ **Francis Economy** : With the aim of initiating a process of global change so that the economy of the present and the future is fairer, fraternal, inclusive and sustainable, the Vatican promotes the event “The Economy of Francesco” (The Economy of Francesco). The meeting will be held from November 19 to 21, 2020. It will bring together young economists and entrepreneurs from around the world. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the international activity that would have been in person in Assisi, Italy, in March, was rescheduled and adapted to the online modality. Therefore, participation will take place through the francescoeconomy.org portal.

³⁵ **Piattaforma Laudato Si** : *The Laudato Si* Initiative Platform of the Dicastery for the Promotion of Integral Human Development is a space in which institutions, communities and families can learn and grow together, as we walk towards full sustainability, in the holistic spirit of integral ecology. We warmly invite you to join this community. Their unique "culture, experience, involvement and talents" are needed on our journey towards a greater love for our Creator, for each other and for the home we share. (LS 14).

2.1 The reality of the parish

In the apostolic exhortation “*Evangelii Gaudium*” Pope Francis dedicated a chapter on the “crisis of community commitment” (EG, 50-109, 2013). In this scenario, the parish is the structure where this evasion of the faithful and the low incidence of ecclesial actions can be most sensitively perceived. By definition, the structural aspect that the parish acquired throughout its history prevails and that has been sacralized until our times, hence the canonical concept prevails: “Parish is a specific community of the faithful, stably constituted in the particular Church, and its pastoral care is entrusted to the parish priest as his own pastor, under the authority of the diocesan Bishop” (CDC, Can. 515 § 1, 1987).

Even with the strength of the legal character in relation to the parish, there was no lack of attempts to reform, renew and reconfigure the parish. The structure that was born in the 4th century, as a presence of the Church in the rural environment, progressively became the structure closest to most of the baptized. In this historical trajectory, we can highlight two milestones: first, the Council of Trent, which consolidated the legal structure, practically unchanged until our times; then, the Second Vatican Ecumenical Council, which, in recovering the value of the Particular Church, is faced with the challenge of implementing a new ecclesiology in a structure gestated in a distinct ecclesial consciousness.

In the search for synodality as pointed out above, the parish appears as a challenge, which makes an effort to seek a pastoral conversion of the parish as pointed out in CNBB document 100 – Community of communities: A new parish. Even with the strong appeal of Aparecida, 2007 for pastoral conversion, after fourteen years, the reality of the parish has changed little or nothing.

2.2 The pastoral conversion of the parish

The Aparecida document had already pointed out the need for a renewal of the parish, when it stated:

“The renewal of the parish at the beginning of the third millennium requires the reformulation of its structures, so that it becomes a network of communities and groups, capable of articulating, achieving that its members truly feel like missionary disciples [...]” (DAP, 172, 2007).

Many studies point to the parish as a structure shaped to the rural reality, which no longer reaches all the demands of the city, because it is an urban culture. In this sense, Pope Francis criticizes self-referentiality, which in the parish seems to establish a vicious circle, consuming all forces in a “pastoral conservation”, where all the vital force of the members is

spent on maintaining “obsolete structures”. For this reason, Aparecida, when summoning the Church of the continent to a process of pastoral conversion and missionary renewal, indicates that this is a commitment of all: “No community should be exempt from entering decisively, with all its strength, in the constant processes of missionary renewal and abandoning outdated structures that no longer favor the transmission of the faith” (DAp 365, 2007).

Indeed, in pointing out synodality as an imperative for the Church in the third millennium, we are not thinking of a new organizational chart of the hierarchy, nor of a democratic system along the lines of elections. Synodality, above all, is an opening for us to walk together, an expression of communion, which can generate new ecclesial structures, but it is not limited to that. Thus, we indicate some topics that can already be implemented by the existing Magisterium and theology, not with the intention of, by itself, realizing the ideal of synodality, but helping to trigger processes that favor this path of conversion and ecclesial communion.

2.3 Pastor, clericalism and self-referentiality

The pastor as the legitimate pastor of the parish carries a great responsibility in government, but as the demands of evangelization grow, this task becomes more burdensome. A consequence of this power concentrated in the figure of the parish priest is the ecclesial anomaly called clericalism, which Pope Francis expresses not only belongs to clerics, but is “a behavior that concerns us all: clericalism is a perversion of the Church” (Francis, 2018).

The parish model, which delegates all decision-making power to the figure of the parish priest, demonstrates that pastoral care in parishes has been undergoing a process of atrophy, causing ecclesial actions to have less and less impact on people's lives. The parish priest is an overworked man, the parish depends on him for all decisions, so the whole process is weakened. Added to this organizational model are considerations about the profile of priests of each era, given that, not long ago, there were documents and texts from the bishops and the **CNP – National Commission of Priests** concerned with the delivery of priests to work, who neglected moments of rest, personal care and even neglected their own health. At the present time, although more objective documents on the subject are lacking, the reality of young clergy seems to be different.

Due to its canonical ordering, the parish favors clericalism, which we can define as this distorted concentration of power over clerics. The consequences are harmful for ecclesial life, since, humanly, the parish priest is demanded so much, to the point that he concentrates impossible tasks for a single person. Thus, in the community, the centralization of the pastoral

care of the parish priests generates a loss of commitment in the members of the parish, as Pope Francis pointed out (EG 102, 2013), stating that they were not trained to assume important responsibilities, and when there is an opportunity, they do not find space in their particular Churches to express and act as such, due to an excessive clericalism that keeps them on the fringes of choices.

The concentration of parish responsibility on the parish priest and the loss of community commitment by the baptized make pastoral action always lacking. In this context, it is impossible to think of initiatives, creative outputs, when it is barely possible to fulfill what already exists. This situation generates what Aparecida described as a vicious cycle of “mere conservation pastoral care” (DAp 370, 2007). This generates a process of involution, in which the community dissolves, since the community principle is to walk together.

We can illustrate this picture with a quote from the XIII Evangelization Plan of the Diocese of Coxim – MS, which listened to over a thousand members of the communities . The text reveals the aspirations dreamed of for that Particular Church:

Humility, acceptance, union, closeness.

The Bishop be united with the Fathers; make more Pastoral Visits. Let the Fathers be welcoming, compassionate, present in pastorals, movements and sectors, visit the sick and the elderly, visit the poor (and not just the rich). Be less administrators and more pastors. The Sisters are present in communities and families; communicate with the most distant and needy, be supportive and sweet. Everyone wants the presence of the Sisters in their own parish. LAY PEOPLE ask for more formation; require more coherence and unity. A special request was that the Fathers stay in the parishes for a long time to continue the activities (Diocese of Coxim XIII Diocesan Plan for Evangelization, 2015).

Finally, the clericalism that imposes the pastoral care of mere conservation suppresses the missionary dimension, so that all efforts are focused on the material structures of the parish. Then, the parish becomes synonymous with its temples, rooms, halls and equipment, normally large and expensive, and, above all, the greatest commitment is no longer placed on evangelization and pastoral care, but on administration and fundraising. Also, as in an attitude of self-preservation, the parish closes in on itself, similarly to the clericalism that closes in on the figure of the parish priest and the self-referentialism in which the community closes in on itself:

“No one builds the future by isolating himself, nor relying only on his own strength, but recognizing himself in the truth of a communion that is always open to encounter, dialogue, listening, mutual help and preserves us from the disease of self- referentiality. ” (Francis, 2014).

2.4 Missionary Ecclesiastical Communities and Private Church

As in the Acts portrait : “They were steadfast in the apostles' teaching, in fraternal communion, in the breaking of bread and in prayers...” (Acts 2:42), community is the most genuine expression of Christians. Parishes emerged later, but although they became the closest ecclesial structure to the baptized, they should not annul or be treated as synonymous with community. The parish is not a community, it is an ecclesial structure, which should articulate the various existing communities in its extension.

The ecclesiology of Vatican II, which recovered the category of the Particular Church, provoked a reflection on communities. In our continent, for example, this movement boosted the development of CEBs, which had already started before the Council. Nevertheless, the Medellín Conference, as a creative reception of the Council, characterized the community as: “local or environmental, which corresponds to the reality of a homogeneous group and which has such a dimension that allows personal and fraternal coexistence among its members” (MD 15). , 10 1968). In this sense, the community has human size, creates bonds and requires conditions of belonging.

In Puebla, 1979, the conscience of the CEBs was well consolidated in the journey of the dioceses of the continent, so, after the number 641 explains the three nouns, the document defines that:

“Basic ecclesial communities are an expression of the Church's preferential love for the simple people; in them his religiosity is expressed, valued and purified and offers him the concrete possibility of participating in the ecclesial task and in the commitment to transform the world” (Puebla, 643, 1979).

The journey of the CEBs triggered many pastoral processes, marked by the protagonism of the laity, with ecclesial actions of great social impact from the perspective of human promotion.

In the 1990s, in the name of a new evangelization, mainly due to the suspicion of Liberation Theology – the theological basis of the CEBs – a weakening of the CEBs was promoted. A “parochialism” was promoted, privileging new movements such as, for example, the Catholic Charismatic Renewal, which strengthened the idea of authority of the figure of the parish priest. Santo Domingo, Episcopal Conference, paradigmatic in this sense, equated these new movements with the height of communities when he presented the following image of the parish: “The parish is a community of communities and movements” (SD 58, 1992).

The stiffening of the authority of the parish priest, the concentration of ecclesial life in the parish, especially in the parish, and the promotion of movements weakened the progress of ecclesial communities. Today, parishes are weakened, as we indicated above, involving fewer and fewer people in community processes, so that the numbers of the latest censuses and static

projections show a vertiginous drop in the number of Catholics. Everything indicates that the quest to concentrate and strengthen the parish structure, nullifying the base communities, has greatly weakened the parishes, instead of strengthening them as expected.

Aparecida 2007 seems to have been a light that was lit as a warning for the Church, as summarized by Father Libânio, in an interview about the Conference: “One of the novelties of the text is the importance it attaches to communities and sees in them the future of revitalizing the Church. It is a theme that runs through the entire Document” (Libânio, 2008). The personal encounter with Jesus Christ is where the missionary-disciple is born, this encounter takes place in the community and founds the community.

The beginning of Pope Francis' pontificate marks a decisive impulse for the whole Church on the path presented in Aparecida. This call is consecrated by the exhortation *Evangelii Gaudium*, in which, precisely in n° 24, the Pope points out the five principles of the life of the communities of missionary disciples: “first”, get involved, accompany, bear fruit and celebrate. The community forms and sends missionary disciples, which in turn, “is the transforming agent of the community, it is through the community of missionary disciples that pastoral conversion and the urgent reconfiguration of the parish are promoted” (Fabio, 2019).

The Church of Brazil, for its fruitful history with the CEBs and accepting the impulses of Aparecida and Pope Francisco, produced several studies and events to recover the value of the community, in the perspective of reconfiguring the parishes. Notably, Document 100 and the new General Guidelines for Evangelizing Action (DGAE) 2019-2023, express the new aspirations for the parish in our time. As Pope Francis said: “The parish is not an outdated structure; precisely because it has great plasticity, it can take on very different forms [...]” (EG 28, 2013), and here is the challenge that challenges parishes at the moment.

Document 100, 2014 “Community of communities: a new parish” presents the pastoral conversion of the parish, in its six chapters, signaling the context of the cultural reality that challenges the structure of the parish. Indeed, in the second chapter, it is interesting to note the note that the Document makes about how the experience of Jesus and his disciples founds communities, the genuine identity of Christianity. The transition from a Church of houses, persecuted and martyred, to a Church with temples, official and expanding, clearly shows how parishes arise and how they evolve in history, the theme of the third chapter.

In the fourth chapter of this Document we find a theological-pastoral foundation of the parish, while in the fifth chapter we have the indication of who the subjects of pastoral conversion are and how they should act, which is so much expected of the parish. And, finally,

in the sixth chapter we have pastoral proposals that are expected in order to trigger the process of reconfiguration of the parish in a community of communities.

The new DGAE 2019-2023 , 2019 explicitly assumes the purpose of recovering the sense of community by presenting the category of the missionary ecclesial community. It is an evolution of the previous categories, not to exclude or deconstruct the ecclesial baggage built up until then, but to incorporate, mainly the missionary key, the outgoing Church. The community is presented with the image of a house, as in the “ *Domus Ecclesiae* ”, where the first Christian communities met. The first chapter is an invitation to deepen the gaze of the disciples in relation to the current world, while the second chapter is a call to deepen the gaze on the disciples themselves in the light of the Master Jesus.

The image of the house that is the community is structured on four pillars – Word, Bread, Charity and Missionary Action – which refer to pastoral axes, respectively: initiation to the Christian life and biblical animation of pastoral care; liturgy and spirituality; service to full life; permanent mission status. It is hoped to recover the sense of community and to promote the process of pastoral conversion, overcoming obsolete structures and the pastoral care of mere conservation. According to the DGAE 2019-2023, the ecclesial missionary community that is structured on these pillars acquires the appearance of the Church of Christ, characterized in the document by the images of the house as: place of meeting; place of tenderness; a place for families and a place with always open doors.

The recovery of this sense of community in the life of the Church makes us understand what Pope Francis proposes when he launches the synod on synodality for the whole Church in all its instances: “The Synod must begin from small communities, from small parishes. This will require patience, work, letting the people speak. The Wisdom of the People of God” (Francis, 2021). There is in the ecclesial community this sacramental character, the power of the Spirit inspires creative responses to current challenges, it is necessary to be open to listening to the Lord who speaks in and through communities.

3. Conclusions

We are living a moment of listening and openness , which as brothers and sisters, we want to respond faithfully to the Lord's mandate to go around the world announcing the Gospel. The Ecclesial Assembly and the Synod on Synodality are privileged spaces for this listening and dialogue. Believing that the great challenge for the implementation of a synodality process in the Church is to combine this style of “walking together” in the parish structure, I venture to suggest some topics that can, in my view, collaborate in this path.

- **Recognize the Ecclesial Missionary Community** as a fundamental unit of the ecclesial base, constituting a canonical statute in relation to the parish.
- **Extinguish or relativize the figure of the parish priest**, promoting the Parish Pastoral Council as the body responsible for the governance of the parish.
- **Establish the Parish Pastoral Council** as an **obligatory** and **deliberative body** in parishes;
- **Place the Economic Affairs Council** in the parish organization chart, as a subordinate of the Parish Pastoral Council;
- **Promoting “Diocesanity”**: the Diocese is the Particular Church and the parishes are structures at service, for this, the unitary path of the diocese must be promoted, notably by unconditional adherence to the Pastoral Plan and the Diocesan Bishop;

Important at this time is listening and dialogue. We can all speak, propose and dream, but at the same time we must be open to listening, welcoming and walking together. I think these attitudes will not only change structures and programs, but actually allow God to speak through his people. Let us live these moments that God gives us, in the same faith that Pope Francis suggests: “a Synod is nothing other than to make explicit what the “*Lumen Gentium*” says: the totality of the People of God is infallible, however, it must be made explicit with faith” (Francisco, 2021).

4 References

ANTUNES DO NASCIMENTO, Fabio. **Parishes without parish priests, is it possible?** At: < <https://amerindiaenlared.org/contenido/11717/paroquias-sem-parocos-e-possible/> > accessed on November 11, 2021.

ENOUGH, Jesus. **“We often see seminarians who seem good, but very rigid. Rigidity is one of our big problems”, Francisco notes** . At: < <http://www.ihu.unisinos.br/609569-vimos-com-frequencia-seminaristas-que-parem-bons-mas-muito-rigidos-a-rigidez-e-um-de-nossos-grandes-problemas-noticed-francisco> > on May 25, 2021.

Code of Canon Law

LATIN AMERICAN EPISCOPAL COUNCIL. *Document of Aparecida. Conclusive text of the V Conference of the Latin American and Caribbean Bishops* . Sao Paulo: Paulus, 2007.

LATIN AMERICAN EPISCOPAL COUNCIL. *CELAM documents. Rio de Janeiro, Medellin, Puebla, Santo Domingo* . Sao Paulo: Paulus, 2005.

IHU Aparecida meant almost a surprise. In: <
<http://www.ihuonline.unisinos.br/artigo/1038-joao-batista-libanio-3>> accessed on November 11, 2021.

SUPERIOR INSTITUTE OF PASTORAL. *Vueltas con la parroquia: balance and perspectives* . Navarre: Divine Word, 2008.

POPE FRANCIS, “Evangeli Gaudium” . *Acta Apostolicae Sedis*, vol.105, n°12 (2013).

POPE FRANCIS. **Commemoration of the Fiftieth Anniversary of the Institution of the Synod of Bishops** . At: <

https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/pt/speeches/2015/october/documents/papa-francesco_20151017_50-anniversario-sinodo.html > accessed November 11, 2021.

PAUL VI, Pope. APOSTOLIC LETTER - APOSTOLIC REQUESTED: *ISTITUZIONE DEL SINODO DEI VESCOVI PER LA CHIESA UNIVERSALE*. At: <

https://www.vatican.va/content/paul-vi/es/motu_proprio/documents/hf_p-vi_motu-proprio_19650915_apostolica-sollicitudo.html > accessed on November 11, 2021.

VaticanNews. Pope: Clericalism is a perversion of the Church.

<https://www.vaticannews.va/pt/papa/news/2018-08/papa-francisco-igreja-clericalismo-jovens-sinodo.html> > accessed November 11, 2021.